

European Research Council
Executive Agency

Established by the European Commission

ERC Data Management Plan

Istanbul Bilgi University

**Nativism, Islamophobia and Islamism in the Age of Populism: Culturalisation and
Religionisation of what is Social, Economic and Political in Europe**

ISLAM-OPHOB-ISM

785934

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ERC OPEN RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (DMP)

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Project Acronym	Project Number
ISLAM-OPHOB-ISM	785934

Template for the ERC Open Research Data Management Plan (DMP)¹. The following sections should describe how you plan to make the project data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR).

Each of the following five issues should be addressed with a level of detail appropriate to the project.

SUMMARY (*dataset² reference and name; origin and expected size of the data generated/collected; data types and formats*)

¹ Based on '[Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in H2020](#)', version 3.0. 26.07.2016, Annex1

² Several datasets may be included into a single DMP.

ISLAM-OPHOB-ISM includes 6 work packages and among these WP2, WP3, WP4, and WP5 are research-based:

- Work Package 1 (WP1). Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP);
- Work Package 2 (WP2). Literature review on responses to globalization;
- Work Package 3 (WP3). Nativisation of resentment against globalization among autochthonous social groups in Europe;
- Work Package 4 (WP4). Islamization of resentment against globalization;
- Work Package 5 (WP5). Synthesis of theory and practice;
- Work Package 6 (WP6). Dissemination.

To explore both Islamism and Islamophobia, ISLAM-OPHOB-ISM employs an interdisciplinary approach, using legal and policy analysis, comparative historical analysis, political claims analysis, socio-economic and cultural analysis, and interview-based analysis.

In addition to academic articles, books, workshops, and conferences ISLAM-OPHOB-ISM will result in datasets, country and comparative reports.

Work Package 1 (WP1). *Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP)*: WP1 is designed to prepare a Data Management Plan (DMP) to efficiently and effectively coordinate the research process. WP1 ensures the technical and administrative quality of the project, the vigorous communication among the members of the research team and efficient treatment of financial, legal and ethical issues.

Work Package 2 (WP2). *Literature review on responses to globalization*: WP2 includes the desk-research on the analysis of radicalization, populism, Islamophobia, Islamism, nativisation, nationalism, heritage, religion, gender, and masculinity. The desk research will include an analysis of the political, cultural, social, and legal debates in Turkey in reference to the Justice and Development Party, and in Morocco in reference to Party of Justice and Development. The data to be analysed are as follows: speeches, statements and official documents of the relevant political actors in Turkey, Morocco, Germany, France, Belgium and the Netherlands. The desk research will have a specific emphasis on the Flemish Block (VB), Alternative für Deutschland (AfD), the Front National (FN), the Party for Freedom (PVV), the Justice and Development Party (JDP) in Turkey, and the Islamist Party for Justice and Development (PJD) in Morocco. A discourse analysis of the speeches, statements and official documents of the relevant political actors will be conducted to shed light on their strategies, discourses, political logic and political style deployed to mobilize masses. These texts and speeches will be analysed using the discourse analysis method with the assistance of native speaker researchers in each country.

Work Package 3 (WP3). *Nativisation of resentment against globalization among autochthonous social groups in Europe*: WP3 includes the conduct of the field research, semi-structured interviews as well as surveys in four European countries, namely Germany, France, Belgium and the Netherlands, to be made with the supporters of the extreme right-wing populist political parties. 50 interviews will be conducted by selected PhD students in

each country (*the selection process is ongoing*). The data will be comprised of interviews transcribed in English.

Work Package 4 (WP4). *Islamization of resentment against globalization*: WP4 includes the conduct of the field research, semi-structured interviews as well as surveys in four European countries namely Germany, France, Belgium and the Netherlands, to be made with the members of immigrant-origin members of the society with moderate and/or strong orientation to Islam. 50 interviews will be conducted by selected PhD students in each country (*the selection process is ongoing*). The data will be comprised of interviews transcribed in English.

The research team has decided that the fieldwork for WP3 and WP4 will be conducted in two stages. This modification to the original proposed plan is intended to align the fieldwork questions with changes in the social, cultural, political contexts of the countries. This ensures that changes impacting the selected communities can be adequately addressed in the research design.

The first stage will be carried out between April-August 2020 and will include interviews with approximately 25 Muslim youth, 25 native youth (18 to 30 years of age) in Germany, France, Belgium and the Netherlands simultaneously. At the first data collection stage approximately 50 interview transcripts will be obtained from each country. In total 200 interview transcripts will be produced in English.

The second stage will be carried out between April-August 2021 and will include interviews with approximately 25 Muslim youth, 25 native youth (18 to 30 years of age) in Germany, France, Belgium and the Netherlands simultaneously. At the second data collection stage approximately 50 interview transcripts will be obtained from each country. In total 200 interview transcripts will be produced in English.

Accordingly, as stated in the proposal, around 400 interviews will be conducted in four countries in the Year 2 and Year 3.

Work Package 5 (WP5). *Synthesis of theory and practice*: WP5 includes the synthesis of theoretical knowledge and the findings of the field research. In WP5; WP2, WP3 and WP4 findings will be synthesized into reports and articles. Therefore, the data collected from the desk research and the interviews will be harvested into open access publications. WP5 will comprise of a discourse analysis of approximately 400 interview transcripts. NVIVO Pro 12 software developed for studies on content analysis will be used to speed up the process and reduce the work load.

Work Package 6 (WP6). *Dissemination*: WP6 includes the dissemination of findings of the research by means of project website, social media, scientific articles, open access repositories, manuscripts, conferences, workshops, country reports, policy briefs, and mainstream media interviews.

1. MAKING DATA FINDABLE (*dataset description: metadata, persistent and unique identifiers e.g., DOI*)

Discoverability of data (metadata provision)

All processed data, once finalised will be made publicly available at Zenodo (www.zenodo.org).

Original 'hard copies' of data (original field research notes) gathered by independent fieldwork investigators will be destroyed upon uploading the original fieldnotes as well as their transcriptions on a secure server hosted by a partner institution located within the EU (European University Institute, Florence, Italy). For file-sharing between the research team comprised on PI (Ayhan Kaya), one full time post-doc researcher (Ayse Tecmen) and one part-time post-doc researcher (Jais Adam-Troian), the EUI set-up an encrypted Microsoft Windows 365. The PI's contact at EUI is Ingo Linsenmann (Ingo.Linsenmann@eui.eu) and Simone Ottaviano (Simone.Ottaviano@eui.eu).

Upon the completion of the project in 31 December 2023, the EUI's ResData Repository (<http://euiresdata.eui.eu/xmlui/>), which was launched in 2017 for the collection, preservation and sharing of digital datasets generated from research projects at the EUI, will be used.

Identifiability of data and standard identification mechanism

We will use DDI (Data Documentation Initiative) which is widely used, international standard for describing data from the social, behavioural, and economic sciences.

- WP 2-6: Qualitative data
 - Data from the project will be uploaded to the open repository Zenodo, for accessibility and public availability.
 - Zenodo offer DOI-numbers for datasets as an identifier. DOI-numbers assigned to datasets will also enable stable and permanent links with DataCite DOI URLs.
 - Zenodo offers versioning support for datasets and can also supply DOI-numbers for each version.
- WP 2-6: Survey data
 - The datasets obtained from European Values Survey, World Values Surveys, and PEW Surveys, will be accompanied by documentation that describes the origin of the data, fieldwork and data collection methods, processing and/or the researcher's management of the data.
- For the processing of the data and the analysis NVivo Pro 12 (".nvp" format extension), SPSS (".sps" format extension), IBM, R, and JAMOVI will be utilized, which uses.

Keywords

- Keywords will be used to increase findability and re-use of registered data sets.

- In order to cover all academic disciplines used in the project and potential users in other academic disciplines, keywords will be selected from different sources.

Naming conventions

- Elements to use in the naming convention are: date of creation, short keyword description, project name, sample or similar depending on the document;
- For the organization of files, we will use a hierarchical file structure. As with file naming, we will use whatever makes most sense to our data, e.g.:
 - Project
 - Date
 - Analysis
 - Location

Clear versioning

- If new versions of registered datasets need to be uploaded Zenodo provides support for version numbers. In that case semantically-versioned tags will be used.

Standards for metadata creation

- Standard metadata fields are provided by Zenodo. Zenodo's metadata is compliant with DataCite's Metadata Schema, and with the option to add keywords uploaded datasets we will fulfil the requirements for being findable and understandable.

2. MAKING DATA OPENLY ACCESSIBLE *(which data will be made openly available and if some datasets remain closed, the reasons for not giving access; where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited (repository?); how the data can be accessed (are relevant software tools/methods provided?))*

Open data:

- Data from WP 1-6, consisting of legal and policy analyses, comparative historical analyses, policy claim analyses, socio-economic and cultural analyses, will be made openly available as the default. Other coded material from these work packages will also be made open and accessible from the EUI's ResData Repository (<http://euiresdata.eui.eu/xmlui/>). Analysis based on results will be published in reports, and academic papers, which will be available on Zenodo. We chose Zenodo because it supports the FAIR principles. The immediate publication at the end of the project aims to minimize the data loss risk.

Closed data:

- Data from WP 3-5, consisting of primary data, such as individual interview data, including interlocutors' personal information and observation data, that is not coded, will be kept closed, as this requires ethics approval and consent by the informant. This kind of raw data will not be made available for reasons of data protection.
- Personal and research data that can lead to the identification of participants (e.g. contact details, interview codes, documents matching interview codes to participants, consent forms) will be classified as confidential and will not be shared with the post-doctoral researchers, the desk researchers, or external parties. The fieldwork researchers in Germany, France, Belgium, the Netherlands and the PI will have access to this data. All interviews will be conducted one-on-one, face-to-face and interlocutors will not be accompanied by family members or friends or associates to ensure the privacy of both interlocutors and researchers.

Software and methods for accessing the data

Standardized instructions for transcription will be provided and all transcripts will be coded in NVivo Pro 12 software. In the upcoming months we will agree on protocols to ensure consistency of coding, node structures and procedures for version control. The post-doctoral researchers (one full time and part time) at Istanbul Bilgi University will use the software. As per the GDPR (2016/679) requirements, researchers based in Turkey will not be allowed to save, or share (through portable devices or e-mail) interview transcripts over Turkey-based internet servers. The PI, as the controller of the data, can authorize the field researchers to access the EUI's file sharing system to upload the anonymized data sets. Data will be analysed in the PI's laptop using the EUI cloud without being downloaded.

As personal data related to vulnerable groups is prone to misuse, any information linked to a specific person and that can be used for retrospective identification will be anonymised from the very early stages of research. The interview materials will be first encrypted and then sent by each field researcher to the PI's EUI Alumni e-mail account (Ayhan.Kaya@eui.eu); the encryption will be done through a WinZip encryption key system. The researchers will receive training in encryption procedures and digital privacy processes. No personal data (such as name, place of birth, localities, family size, specific diseases, injuries or diagnoses, or any other specific contact information linking to a specific person) will be asked during the interviews. Other similar information that is not needed for analysis will be avoided. If any such information is mentioned by the participant, it will be anonymised in the transcribed material.

In January 2020, fieldwork researchers who will be PhD students will attend a mandatory 2-day

orientation in Istanbul, Turkey which will train them on the ethics and the mechanics of data collection, access, sharing and storage.

3. MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE (*which standard or field-specific data and metadata vocabularies and methods will be used*)

Are the data produced in the project interoperable, that is allowing data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc. (i.e. adhering to standards for formats, as much as possible compliant with available (open) software applications, and in particular facilitating re-combinations with different datasets from different origins)?

- WP 1-6: [Currently under development] We aim to reach an interoperable level by using open file formats that are easily available (e.g. rtf., doc., csv, and xls).
- WP 3-5: NVIVO Pro 12 with English vocabulary and documentation.

For research data generated in ISLAM-OPHOB-ISM (785934), the metadata will be based on a generalised metadata schema as the one used in Zenodo, which includes elements such as:

- Title: free text
- Creator: Last name, first name
- Date
- Subject: Choice of keywords and classifications
- Description: Text explaining the content of the data set and other contextual information needed for the correct interpretation of the data,
- Format: Details of the file format,

- Resource Type: data set, image, audio, etc.,
- Identifier: DOI,
- access rights: closed access, embargoed access, restricted access, open access.

4. INCREASE DATA RE-USE (*what data will remain re-usable and for how long, is embargo foreseen; how the data is licensed; data quality assurance procedures*)

How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?

- We will apply a Creative Commons Attributions 4.0 (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>) or specify a different license and access level found appropriate, as found in Zenodo.org. [Currently under development]

When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

- WP 2-5,6: Data will be made available immediately after publishing.
- WP 1: Data will be made available in line with dates for deliverables, as specified in the project.

Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.

How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

- Unlimited time period.
- Interview transcripts (anonymised) will be available on EUI's ResData repository after the completion of the project

Are data quality assurance processes described?

Throughout the project, clear and accurate records of the research procedures, and the results obtained, will be kept, including interim results. The gathered data will be transferred and shared within/between the PI and post-doc researchers through European University Institute's encrypted Microsoft Windows 365 data sharing site. As per the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, 2016/679), the confirmation of compliance will be issued by the legally responsible person of the EUI, and it will be delivered to the ERCEA in the second year. All network traffic to and from the system is SSL-encrypted. Access to the project-specific site is limited to the project research team who will be provided specific user identities. When this is not possible due to technical reasons (e.g. poor internet connectivity), data will be shared through hardware copy during the project meetings. We will develop a detailed strategy for procedures for data collection, storage, protection, transfer, among others, shared with all researchers.

5. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES and DATA SECURITY (*estimated costs for making the project data open access and potential value of long-term data preservation; procedures for data backup and recovery; transfer of sensitive data and secure storage in repositories for long term preservation and curation*)

The costs are limited to the work needed to put together and describe the dataset.

How will these be covered?

- Currently under development.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

- The PI along with the full time and the part-time post-doc researcher at Istanbul Bilgi University is responsible for updating the data management plan, which will be discussed regularly at the weekly project meetings. EUI will be consulted on a regular basis regarding the sharing of data among the research team and the storage of data sets upon the project's completion.

Roles and responsibilities

- Data capture and metadata production: PI, the full time, the part-time post-doc researcher at Istanbul Bilgi University, and 4 fieldwork researchers (1 in Germany, 1 in France, 1 in Belgium, 1 in the Netherlands) and 1 desk researcher in Morocco.
- Data quality: PI, the full time, the part-time post-doc researcher at Istanbul Bilgi University
- Storage and backup: Country fieldwork data will be stored and backed up in the EUI server through its file-sharing service. As per the GDPR (2016/679) requirements, researchers based in Turkey will not be allowed to save, or share interview transcripts over Turkey-based internet servers. All studies on the interview transcripts will be made online on the EUI's file-sharing system. The PI will keep copies of the transcriptions on his EUI alumni e-mail (Ayhan.Kaya@eui.eu) and the EUI will be responsible for the safe-keeping of data sets obtained from the fieldwork.
- Data archiving: European University Institute, Florence

Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)?

- Istanbul Bilgi University will provide a central source of information, guidance and contacts on research data management. European University Institute, Florence will provide IT, storage, and access tools to deliver the data management plan. Following completion of the project, the dataset will be securely archived at the EUI server for at least 10 years. This will ensure safe margin for future audit.

DISCLAIMER. Please note that the ERC Data Management Plan is not a part of the Ethics Review. It is the responsibility of the Principal Investigator to inform the ERCEA Ethics Team of any ethics issues/concerns regarding the collection, processing, sharing and storage of data in relation to the project. The Principal investigator can also be asked to submit an Ethics Data Management Plan (Ethics DMP).